

Sociocultural competence of students -philologists studying Russian language

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Annotation. The article is devoted to one of the most pressing problems of modern methods of teaching Russian to philologists with Uzbek as the language of instruction. The article highlights issues of the importance of socio-cultural aspects in the development of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language. The methods of teaching philology students are analyzed from the point of view of the effectiveness of its application for the formation of students' communicative competence.

Key words : teaching methods, globalization, internationalization, socio-cultural approach, sociocultural competence , national culture, dialectical method, intercultural communication

World education is gradually beginning to develop in the context of a dialogue of cultures. The main goal of modern education is not just to prepare a highly professional specialist in a particular field, but also a comprehensively developed person of culture, capable and ready to communicate and cooperate with people of different nationalities, religions and cultures, a person who has absorbed the wealth of the cultural heritage of his people and the peoples of other countries, striving for mutual understanding with them, capable and ready to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication.

One of the strategic tasks in the period of globalization of the modern educational space is the education of a comprehensively developed and harmonious generation. Intensive communication processes of the modern world in the educational process force us to evaluate the role and importance of the Russian language as a foreign language in a different way. Today it is impossible to imagine the formation of a highly qualified specialist without knowledge of any foreign language.

Globalization of the modern educational space implies the formation of foreign language speech communications in students, allowing them to speak and communicate freely in another socio-cultural environment . In teaching Russian , students primarily encounter not linguistic problems, but factors that determine the social, everyday and cultural spheres of the country of the studied language. Therefore, modern methods of teaching Russian should include socio-cultural aspects and approaches to teaching the language, because only on its basis can the effect of linguacultural immersion be achieved .

Modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language, as the results of the study show, should include socio-cultural aspects, which allows students studying Russian to adapt more quickly in any multicultural environment.

The idea that is used in practice in the educational process in Russian language lessons, that is, teaching students Russian with the study of the cultural and everyday life of native speakers, is not new today, but, unfortunately, in the methodological aspect it is not yet fully used. Methodologists-teachers believe that the learning process should include only real socio-cultural conditions of communication, in this case - the conditions of the country whose language is to be studied.

It has become fashionable for modern youth to read fiction in the original, watch films in a foreign language. Many respondents explain that this is the desire of young people to more deeply understand the history and established cultural traditions of these states. Of course, this is undoubtedly true, first

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of all, these features are expressed through language. Therefore, in our scientific research, the main emphasis falls on the linguistic component, as the most significant component in the cultural system [1].

The reforms and changes that are being implemented in education, economics and state policy have made modern society more open, which in turn has led to changes in the teaching of Russian as a foreign language: today, live communication and analysis of specific speech situations necessary in everyday life are most in demand. It should be noted that the socio-cultural approach was taken into account earlier in language teaching, and therefore more attention should be paid to this aspect in the educational process.

Why is the socio-cultural approach a necessary part of the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language? The socio-cultural approach in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language is a direction that incorporates not only the philological aspect, but also the study of the country itself, its culture, rituals and customs of life, the history of the language being studied.

T. Yu. Nazarenko notes the main objective of this direction in her research, the socio-cultural approach in the methodology of teaching the Russian language: "is the study of linguistic units that most vividly reflect the national characteristics of the culture of the people - the native speaker, that is, realities. Ideas and necessary information about other peoples and countries are formed on the basis of stereotypes. Such stereotypes can be conveyed through key words and concepts, and this is how the linguistic picture of the world reflects its cultural picture" [1].

Ovsyannikova T.A. rightly notes that "each ethnic culture has its own unique structure and its own logic, and only on the basis of this logic can one explain what is of fundamental importance for a given culture and what is of secondary importance.

It is obvious that the interrelations of its various structural elements and behavioral components are individual for each ethnic group, for each ethnic culture" [4]. Therefore, knowledge of the language of a given people is a kind of hint to discovering the secrets of the culture of the ethnic group speaking this language. Language is not only a means of communication and expression of thought, but also a perception of cultural values. Language reflects the experience and life of the people, its history, material and spiritual culture. We can call the reality of this time multicultural, when communication occurs between people belonging to nations speaking different languages

"Language teaching, combined with familiarization with the historical and ethnographic features of the country of the language being studied, can and should become a powerful means of mutual understanding between peoples. Also, the formation of linguistic and linguacultural competence is valuable for enriching one's own culture: communication, speech, mental work" [2].

The idea of the relationship between national culture and language is beyond doubt for many educational researchers and has long been used in foreign language teaching methods. Although the vast majority of educational institutions continue to use teaching materials that involve cramming texts that are not relevant or interesting to students.

Today, thanks to the openness of the educational and cultural space, interest in the history, ethnography and everyday life of the countries of the studied language has increased significantly. This interest, as a motivator, must be used in the construction of teaching methods, studying the Russian language in parallel with the national culture of the country of the studied language

In our opinion, when developing educational methods, it is necessary to take into account and rely on the following principles: content, communication, cognition, culture. "Since language, thinking and

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culture are inextricably linked, this principle implies the possibility of “acting” in other cultures through teaching in the language of these cultures.

A good result is achieved by using a method in which the language is integrated with other subjects. This experiment can last for about two months. It includes various classes in the classroom and a visit to the city's Museum of Local History. Before visiting the museum, the main concepts and principles were studied. The visit to the museum included enrichment and expansion of the activity. The students were given handouts with instructions in a foreign language, as well as a bilingual glossary that can be used during the visit.

The positive effects achieved by the end of the project were: improvement of the students’ general target language competence, increase in students’ motivation, development of their multilingual interests and views, and access to the target language terminology for a specific subject [6].

The sociocultural approach to language teaching was used by a number of academic researchers to teach students studying Russian in the first year of the philological program with Uzbek instruction. By the methodology they developed, the study of a foreign language took place directly through familiarization with Russian culture, which was completely new for the students. In achieving the successful formation of this competence, it is precisely communicativeness that plays a major role, which in turn focuses on the inclusion of students in the direct act of communication with each other (or with the teacher) to solve life problems that arise in the course of "changing reality [7]. This is successfully achieved in those language trainings where increased attention is paid to listening comprehension and speaking, since writing (reading) and oral speech of any person are quite different [2].

This approach has become widespread, because it copes well with the task of overcoming the language barrier, helps to memorize the necessary cliched phrases, etc. But on the other hand, this method is not free from shortcomings, which, first of all, practicing teachers include, superficiality in learning the language, as well as the linguistic incompetence of students, "since, according to Tlevtsezhev M.A., it does not pay sufficient attention to the grammatical side of speech, pronunciation, mainly it is a mechanical reproduction of speech models [8].

"Despite the lack of a holistic approach to solving the problem of effective teaching of foreign languages, this approach remains in demand today, that is, some strategies are used in the communicative methodology that meet the needs of society. Such strategies primarily include the use of the information gap in foreign language speech practice" [8, p. 180].

Today, we can talk about “the development of new approaches and pedagogical methods in teaching Russian as a foreign language, which will be specifically aimed at integrating this subject with the block of humanitarian disciplines based on multiculturalism .

Based on the above, we can conclude that the sociocultural approach to teaching Russian as a foreign language is extremely necessary, as it allows students to perceive the language in conjunction with the culture, traditions, history, religion, and everyday behavior of the people whose language they are studying.

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